

USE OF VITAMIN D IN THE TREATMENT OF POSTCOVID ALOPECIA

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In studies, about 20% of people who had COVID-19 later developed temporary hair shedding, which usually begins a few months after recovery from COVID-19. If you have hair shedding, you'll see many more hairs than usual fall out all over your scalp.

The hair shedding can occur a few months after you experience a stressful event or illness, especially an illness that causes a fever. Because COVID-19 causes a fever, some people see excessive hair shedding after they recover.

People also develop excessive hair shedding after they recover from other diseases like pneumonia, scarlet fever, and the flu.

Most people regrow their hair over a period of several months without treatment.

Alopecia areata can flare after stress or illness

If you have alopecia areata, it's possible to have a flare-up after recovering from COVID-19.

In Italy, researchers found that 42.5% of people who had alopecia areata and developed COVID-19 saw their alopecia areata flare. By comparison, 12.5% of people who had alopecia areata and didn't get COVID-19 had a flare-up.

When do hair shedding and alopecia areata start?

Hair shedding usually begins 2 to 3 months after you get COVID-19. In one study that looked at hair loss after COVID-19, hair shedding often began after 56 days, so a little under two months.

A flare-up of alopecia areata can begin earlier. In studies, most people had a flare-up 1 to 3 months after getting COVID-19.

How long do hair shedding and alopecia areata last?

Hair shedding usually lasts 3 to 6 months, and then hair starts regrowing on its own.

Predicting how long hair loss due to alopecia areata can last is more difficult. Many people, especially children, regrow their hair without treatment. Some people who have alopecia areata need treatment to help their hair regrow.

Relevance

In diffuse alopecia, hair loss occurs evenly across the entire scalp due to a disruption in the normal hair growth cycle. Hair falls out intensively every day, but usually, it does not lead to complete baldness. Vitamin D deficiency is associated with a decrease in immune system functionality and supports autoimmune inflammation in diffuse alopecia.

Aim of the study

To evaluate the clinical efficacy of vitamin D in combination therapy for women with diffuse alopecia and its impact on their immune system.

Materials and Methods

The study involved 95 women aged 17-45 with diffuse alopecia. In the main group (50 patients), a complex therapy including D3 capsules was used, while the control group (45 patients) received traditional therapy. Serum levels of vitamin D were measured using immunochemiluminescent analysis.

Results

In the main group of 60 patients:

- Severe vitamin D deficiency was identified in 28 (48%) patients.
- Deficiency in 16 (32%).
- Insufficiency in 9 (18%).

In the control group of 48 patients:

- Severe deficiency in 22 (42.2%).
- Deficiency in 13 (31.1%).
- Insufficiency in 12 (26.7%).

After 8 weeks of therapy, levels were restored in 37 (74%) patients from the main group and 24 (53.4%) patients from the control group. Clinical recovery was observed in 35 (70%) patients from the main group and 21 (46.6%) in the control group.

Conclusions

The use of vitamin D led to immune system recovery in 75% of cases and improved therapy outcomes for diffuse alopecia in 80% of patients.

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